

GENDER SOCIALISATION THROUGH DEVELOPMENTAL ASSETS

*Dr. Sunita Jain**Assistant Professor**MES's Pillai College of Education and Research Chembur*

“You cannot find peace by avoiding life.”

— *Virginia Woolf*

Developmental Assets are gateway towards harmony and peace. The Developmental Assets are 40 research-based, positive qualities that influence young people’s development, helping them become caring, responsible, and productive adults. The framework has been adapted to be developmentally relevant from early childhood through adolescence.

Gender Socialisation is still a challenge in most of the schools and colleges. The influence of family, religion, society, culture has a great impact on the child’s development. It can be either positive or negative depending on the exposure and impact of different forces on the child. School and teachers need to intervene and take the onus of positive gender socialization and overcome the prejudices if any. This will definitely lead to an empowered child.

An empowered child is characterized by the lack of conflict behaviors and the freedom from fear of violence. It develops a state of mind which gives them freedom to pursue their dreams and imagination. It gives them confidence to take decisions and develop problem-solving skills. They are equipped to use their resources in optimum manner. Gender will not become a barrier at any instance for them.

Need of the study

Our children need to be made aware of the gender issues which is still prevalent in both urban and rural India. Though the recent political movements were in favour of LGBT rights but still there is a lot of differences in each one’s mindset about LGBT as well as male and female rights too. Students and teachers play an important role in creating a ripple effect in today’s scenario. If they are trained well with positive gender socialisation, it will have its own seep in young minds.

Review of Related Literature

A. Developmental Assets

Chew, Wesley and others (Feb 2010) finds out that possessing high numbers of developmental assets greatly reduces the likelihood of a young person engaging in health-risk behaviors. Since youth in the juvenile justice system seem to exhibit many high-risk behaviors, the purpose of this study was to assess the presence of external, internal, and social context areas of developmental assets in at-risk youth attending a northeast Missouri juvenile justice center. **Methods:** Male and female middle and high school students moved to a residential juvenile justice center voluntarily completed the Developmental Assets Profile (DAP) instrument during a regularly scheduled "intake" session. **Results:** Most respondents reported lacking risk-protective factors in the internal and social context areas. Respondents noted their lack of community involvement in the social context area and their over involvement with negative influences in the internal context area. Specifically in the internal and external context areas, most respondents reported having trouble with substance abuse and not having positive peer or parental support. In the social context area, many noted that they wanted to do well in activities and were encouraged to do well; however, they scored service to others and involvement in religious groups or activities as low. **Conclusions:** Students who lack protective qualities, especially those who do not feel committed to their

community, are more likely to be involved in substance abuse and risky behaviors. School-community partnerships may provide the targeted health protective factors that encourage more community involvement and more positive health behaviors in these youth.

Scales, Peter C and others (Mar 2013) implemented "Kishoree Kontha" ("Adolescent Girls' Voices") in Bangladeshi villages to build the developmental assets (e.g., support from others, social competencies) of rural girls through peer education in social skills, literacy, and school learning. The Developmental Assets Profile (DAP) measured the project's impact on ecological and individual assets. Analysis of two cohorts involving more than 600 intervention and 400 control adolescents ("M" [subscript age] = 13.5) showed a significant increase in project girls' developmental assets, with an average effect size, net of contamination and control group scores, of 0.80. The results suggest the Project's effectiveness in improving human and social capital for vulnerable adolescent girls living in rural Bangladesh villages, and the utility of the DAP as a cross-culturally relevant measurement tool.

Stevens, Holly; Wilkerson, Kevin (Apr 2010) defined Developmental Assets as the positive building blocks that all children and adolescents need to succeed. The article examines the usefulness of the Developmental Assets for a comprehensive, developmental, and strengths-based school counseling program. A crosswalk comparing the Developmental Assets to the American School Counselor Association's National Standards illustrates that the Developmental Assets complement the academic and personal/social domains but lack a substantial career component.

B. Gender Socialisation

Chinen, Marjorie and Elmeski, Mohammed (2016) conducted an impact evaluation of The United Nations Children's Emergency Fund's (UNICEF's) teacher-training program and reinforcing text messages that aim to provide meaningful knowledge regarding the transformative potential of positive gender socialization in education for peace building in the region of Karamoja, Uganda. The impact evaluation assessed the effects of the teacher-training program, with an emphasis on gender socialization, on teachers' knowledge, attitudes, and practices concerned with gender equity, and positive gender socialization. The authors implemented a mixed-methods research design for the impact evaluation, using quantitative and qualitative methods. They compared the outcomes of interest among the teachers who benefit from the program with the outcomes of interest of comparable teachers in different schools who do not benefit from the program.

Sapru, Saloni (2006) examined the ancestral and acculturated cultural meanings in immigrant Indian parenting and adolescent identity using the independence-interdependence dimension as the focus. Forty Indian parents and their adolescents in Delhi, India, and Geneva, Switzerland, were interviewed using open-ended questions and scenarios. Adolescents also completed a contextual version of the Twenty Statements Test. Results showed beliefs and practices to be similar for the two groups of parents except that immigrant parents in Geneva placed greater emphasis on traditional Indian culture at home. Self-other constructions of identity measures showed Geneva adolescents to have fewer attributes of interdependence compared to their counterparts in Delhi. Case study analysis further demonstrated how immigrant adolescents construct their self-other relations to synthesize the ancestral and acculturated values of their parents and the host society.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

- 1) To create a relation between developmental assets and gender socialization
- 2) To suggest practices for teachers and parents based on developmental assets which will foster positive gender socialisation

ACTIVITIES SUGGESTED FOR STUDENT TEACHERS BASED ON DEVELOPMENTAL ASSETS.:

 SUPPORT

1. Family support-Family life provides high levels of love and support.
 - Have home visits , invite parents in school for discussion, debate, workshops etc .
2. Positive family communication-Young person and her or his parent(s) communicate positively, and young person is willing to seek advice and counsel from parents.
 - Conduct workshops and seminars to train the parents for positive gender communication.
3. Other adult relationships-Young person receives support from three or more nonparent adults.
 - Train students to conduct talks/ debates for their relatives and close friends
 - Reflection on movie reviews and advertisements which portray gender discrimination
4. Caring school climate-School provides a caring, encouraging environment.
 - Create a code of conduct which encourages positive gender socialization
 - Care should be taken that neither scholastic nor non scholastic activities encourage any type of gender discrimination
5. Parent involvement in schooling-Parent(s) are actively involved in helping young person succeed in school.
 - Invite parents for sessions, workshops etc for gender discrimination issues.
 - Encourage teachers for home visit

✚ EMPOWERMENT
6. Community values youth, youth as resources -Young person perceives that adults in the community value youth, useful roles in the community
 - Engage students for street plays
 - Use social media like Facebook, Twitter etc to voice their opinion
 - Train students to advocate people in the society about gender socialization

✚ BOUNDARIES AND EXPECTATIONS
7. Family boundaries-Family has clear rules and consequences and monitors the young person's whereabouts.
 - At home , parents need to take care that not only them but also no family members or relatives encourage stereotyping
8. School boundaries-School provides clear rules and consequences.
 - School authorities should be very vigilant that there is no scope of gender discrimination in any activities conducted.
 - It's always advisable to practice than preach
 - Teachers needs to be trained through various seminars and workshops to bridge a gap between gender discrimination
9. Neighborhood boundaries-Neighbors take responsibility for monitoring young people's behavior.
 - In our country, neighbors too play a active role to be in compliance or non compliance with several gender issues. So it's better to be vocal about several issues, discuss with close people in the neighbourhood so that each one can be more aware and be concerned about several issues prevailing in the society.
10. Adult role models-Parent(s) and other adults model positive, responsible behavior.
 - As a parent, teacher and responsible adult , it's very important that we reflect and ponder on our daily communication and action which should not mislead our young generation students. Avoid gender bias in communication and writing. Start replacing the term Chairman with chairperson, Policeman with Police Officer etc to encourage gender neutral languages.

Relation among Developmental Assets and empowering Young minds with positive gender socialisation.

Our daily experience in life, prejudices formed, influence of various societal, cultural forces sometimes engulf us in dilemma to understand the difference between positive and negative gender socialization. If parents, teachers and students work in tandem, we can dream of a better society and a better future for the generations to come. And to do so mastering developmental assets will become a powerful tool to create an ideal society, free from the clutches of gender bias.

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